

Impact of Entrainment on Information Processing in a Generic Model of Some Inner Ear

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Abstract. Mechanical processing in the hearing organ and mechano-electrical transduction are two essential elements in the sensory processing of sound. Hair cell motility (bundle- or somatic motility) are considered to play a key role in creating a high sensitivity, selectivity and dynamic range - and ultimately enable communication in complex acoustical environments, matched to the species under study. While it is well known that the auditory system is highly nonlinear, only few beneficial effects of nonlinear behaviour have been identified. In this study we use “generic” numerical models of oscillating systems to quantify the impact of nonlinear dynamic effects on information processing in the auditory system. The rationale behind is to identify ubiquitous phenomena in nonlinear dynamic systems rather than focusing on phenomena within a specific species. We used coupled second-order systems with an intrinsic gradient in the natural periodicity in the absence and presence of an external driving force. The results show that entrainment clusters can be diversified using time-dependent metrics and statistical moments. Deviating from previous studies, elements of clusters show identical mean periodicity, but heavily skewed distributions, dependent on their position in the cluster. It can furthermore be shown that information encoding of an external driving force breaks with a strict tonotopic organization of the system. Ubiquitous effects might help to overcome current challenges in our understanding of hearing. On a longer perspective, these results can identify relevant assumptions to re-consider in the description of the sense of hearing.

INTRODUCTION

The ability to process information from sound, even in complex acoustical environments, is an outstanding ability of the auditory system. This is especially true for mammalian hearing which is able to separate the sound received from simultaneously active sources into individual objects [1]. Any damage to the auditory system heavily reduces or even abolishes this ability. One especially important element in auditory processing of mammalian and many non-mammalian species is the inner ear with its active outer hair cells (OHC) and the mechano-electrical transduction mechanism that translates mechanical oscillations into action potentials. Healthy OHC have been linked to the presence of amplification, compression and high sensitivity and selectivity [2]. Damage to the OHC leads to loss of sensitivity, reduction in compression and the inability to communicate in complex acoustical environments.

The healthy inner ear of many species emits spectrally narrow sounds in the presence or absence of acoustic stimulation [3]. These oto-acoustic emissions (OAEs) are highly dependent on OHC function and vanish or are heavily reduced in the case of OHC damage. Spontaneous OAEs (SOAEs) reflect self-sustained inner ear oscillations and interact with behavioural measures of, among other, pure tone sensitivity [4] and loudness at low stimulus intensities [5]. In amphibians, hair bundle motility has been studied extensively [6] and could be a source of SOAE in these species. Similar to SOAE, the intrinsic periodicity of hair bundles be entrained to the periodicity of an external stimulus [7]. SOAEs also show entrainment effects across ears of lizards [8]. These data are in good agreement with the phenomenon of entrainment of a limit cycle oscillator in a broad variety of experiments in physical and biological systems, independent of the type of oscillator and the time- or length scale of the system under study. Even though the mechanism of hair cell motility differs between amphibian and mammalian species, the presence of SOAE can be considered as a joint phenomenon with highly similar properties in the presence or absence of stimulation. While filter-based models of the inner ear are, by design, incapable of reproducing OAEs, a number of attempts exist to include the increased complexity provided by coupled oscillators compared to filter banks in models of hearing [9, 10, 11]. One class of such models is capable of producing various types of OAE, including SOAE and can, with the use of simplified assumptions, even reproduce behavioural data connected to the interaction of self-sustained oscillations (underlying SOAE) and perception [9, 12]. Interestingly, this class of models also shows a broad variety of phenomena connected to entrainment [13]. Studies of oscillations of individual cells provide important details about the dynamical properties of OHCs. But the results of these studies are challenging to transfer into the actual scale of the hearing system with hundreds or thousands of hair cells and the surrounding coupled structures. Studies of complex

models of the hearing organ on the other side are more straight forward to connect to data observable in humans, but suffer from the challenge to link overall dynamics to the individual elements.

This study postulates that entrainment and connected phenomena are a relevant factor in healthy hearing. Because damage to the hearing systems leads to loss of phenomena that could be connected to entrainment, one might speculate that the inability to form auditory objects is caused by the inability of the damaged (and potentially aided) inner ear to utilize entrainment as information encoding strategy. To shed light on the role of entrainment on information processing in hearing, the present study uses generic models of inner ear processing based on coupled, nonlinear and active oscillators. These models describe self-sustained oscillating systems on either single-cell level (amphibian hair bundle) or compound level (inner ear oscillations) underlying SOAE. The role of self-organization in such dynamical systems is linked to the processing of information in the presence and absence of external stimuli. The results of this study will provide information about the impact of the postulated entrainment effect of characteristics accessible through SOAE measurements, and how the presence of entrainment affects encoding of information across oscillating elements. It will also provide insights into how such a system encodes an external stimulus across an imposed tonotopic axis as present in mammalian inner ears.

METHODS

The numerical systems were implemented in JULIA [14]. Each system consisted of $N = 80$ oscillators described by an individual equation of motion. The parameters were adjusted such that each oscillator in isolation displays a limit cycle in phase space. The intrinsic periodicity of the oscillators was adjusted such that the system of oscillators showed a gradient between the first and the last oscillator in the system. Coupling was introduced to nearest neighbours, and the driving force was applied to all oscillators simultaneously. The first and last oscillator in the system were subject to free boundary conditions.

One set of systems was based on the model presented by [15] to model Lizard SOAE, based on a simplified Ginzburg-Landau equation (GL). The equation of motion of the n -th oscillator was given by:

$$\dot{z}_n(t) = (\varepsilon_n + j\omega_n)z_n(t) - B_n|z_n(t)|^2z_n(t) + F_{d_n}(t) + F_{c_n}(t) \quad z(t) = x(t) + \frac{j}{\omega}\dot{x}(t) \quad (1)$$

The real part of z_n can be interpreted as the position x , and the imaginary part as the velocity \dot{x} of the oscillator. The parameters ε_n and B_n control the speed of convergence to the limit cycle and the non-linearity, respectively. The parameter ω_n controls the periodicity of the limit cycle. This type of oscillator shows a circular limit cycle in phase space. $F_{d_n}(t)$ and $F_{c_n}(t)$ represent the external driving force and the force imposed by nearest-neighbour coupling, respectively. The driving force was applied to all oscillators simultaneously. Nearest-neighbour coupling is described by:

$$F_{c_n}(t) = (d_n + jk_n)(z_{n+1} + z_{n-1} - 2z_n) \quad \forall n \in [2, N-1], k_n \in \mathbb{R}, d_n \in \mathbb{R} \quad (2)$$

The second set of systems was based on van der Pol oscillators (VP), previously used to describe generic aspects of otoacoustic emissions (but rejected as a specific model of mammalian cochlear mechanics) [16].

To ensure the same shape of the limit cycle for all oscillators in the system while modifying their periodicity, a modified version of the equation of motion was used [17]:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_n(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}_n(t) \\ \dot{y}_n(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \omega y_n(t) \\ \omega\mu(1 - x_n^2(t))y_n(t) - \omega x_n(t) + F_{d_n}(t) + F_{c_n}(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{with} \quad y_n(t) = \dot{x}_n(t) \quad (3)$$

Nearest-neighbour coupling was introduced by:

$$F_{c_n}(t) = k_n(x_{n+1}(t) + x_{n-1}(t) - 2x_n(t)) + d_n(\dot{x}_{n+1}(t) + \dot{x}_{n-1}(t) - 2\dot{x}_n(t)) \quad \forall n \in [2, N-1], k_n \geq 0, d_n \in \mathbb{R} \quad (4)$$

The dynamics of an oscillator can be characterised by the rotation number ρ in phase space:

$$\rho = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \frac{d}{dt'} \angle(x(t) + j\dot{x}(t)) dt' = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \iota(t) dt' \quad (5)$$

FIGURE 1. Systems of 80 coupled oscillators without external forcing. Panels A-C show systems composed of VP oscillators, panels D-F systems composed of GL oscillators. The first, second, and third rows shows systems without coupling (A,D), with dissipative coupling (B,E), and with dissipative- and reactive coupling (C,F). The dashed line shows the intrinsic periodicity of the oscillators. The solid line the average frequency derived through the instantaneous winding number t . The red lines show the distribution of t for each oscillator.

In the numerical calculation of average frequency, the integral was replaced by the the unwrapped phase at time T minus the unwrapped phase at time 0. The kernel of the integral will be referred to as "instant rotation number" t throughout the rest of the paper. The instant rotation number is thus calculated by having T go towards 0 instead of ∞ and will in practice be a single simulation time step.

Information in the oscillation of the system was quantified using mutual information with the unit of bits [18]. Mutual information of two signals $x_m(t)$ and $x_n(t)$ is related to the entropy $H(\cdot)$ of two signals:

$$I(x_n(t), x_m(t)) = H(x_n(t)) + H(x_m(t)) - H(x_n(t), x_m(t)) \quad (6)$$

Where $H(x_n(t))$ describes the entropy of signal $x_n(t)$ and $H(x_n(t), x_m(t))$ describes the joint entropy of the two signals $x_n(t)$ and $x_m(t)$:

$$H(x_n) = - \sum_{x_n \in \mathcal{X}_n} p(x_n) \log_2 p(x_n) \quad (7)$$

$$H(x_n, x_m) = - \sum_{x_n \in \mathcal{X}_n} \sum_{x_m \in \mathcal{X}_m} p(x_n, x_m) \log_2 p(x_n, x_m) \quad (8)$$

with $\mathcal{X}_n, \mathcal{X}_m$ representing the set of possible amplitudes in signals $x_n(t)$ and $x_m(t)$, respectively. The mutual information is always finite and quantifies the amount of information that is contained in both $x_n(t)$ and $x_m(t)$. In the tested systems, mutual information was quantified between the amplitude of two neighboured oscillators $x_{n'}(t)$ and $x_{n'-1}(t)$, and between each oscillator $x_{n'}(t)$ and the time signal of the driving force $F_d(t)$.

RESULTS

Figure 1 shows the state of two systems of coupled oscillators. Figure 1A,B show systems of VP oscillators in the absence and presence of coupling, respectively. Figure 1D-F show systems of GL oscillators in the absence and presence of coupling, respectively. In the absence of a driving force, the system of oscillators evolved into a state with groups of oscillators getting entrained into the same periodicity, forming a cluster. Both systems show clusters, in line with previous findings. The analysis of t in short time frames revealed the presence of "tails" in the distribution of t at the edges of each cluster. While t was constant within each cluster, oscillators differed strongly in their temporal dynamics with long and thin tails pointing away from the nearest cluster. These tails were broader in the system of VP (B) than in the system of GL oscillators (D). In the time domain, oscillators with a long tail showed periodic strongly non-harmonic oscillations, while oscillators in the middle of a cluster showed a close-to harmonic oscillation pattern.

Figure 2 shows the state of the systems from Figure 1, but in the presence of a harmonic driving force applied to all oscillators. In the presence of a driving force, a cluster formed with an average periodicity corresponding to the

FIGURE 2. Same as Fig. 1, but in the presence of a sinusoidal driving force. The strength of dissipative and reactive coupling of the systems in each column is provided by the real and imaginary part of the complex number on top, respectively. The first column (A-C) are results for systems of coupled VP oscillators with a non-linearity of $\mu = 1$. The second and third columns (D-I) are results for systems of GL oscillators with the non-linearity parameters of $(\epsilon, B) = (4.0, 1)$ and $(\epsilon, B) = (1.0, 1)$, respectively. The rows are results for three different amplitudes of the external driving force.

inverse of the driving force frequency. The size of the cluster depended on the amplitude of the driving frequency, with a stronger driving force leading to a bigger cluster. Additional clusters formed close to, but not identical to the periodicity of the clusters in the un-driven system. Clusters with periodicity lower than the driving force periodicity deviated more from the clusters formed in the un-driven system than clusters with periodicity higher than the driving force periodicity. Similar to the un-driven systems, each cluster was accompanied by tails in the distribution of ι . With increasing amplitude of the driving force, the tails became less sharp, also for clusters remote from the driving periodicity. Especially the clusters located at frequencies above the driving frequency show large deviations. Clusters in the GL systems were more robust towards the driving force compared to the VP systems (A-C). For the GL systems, clusters were broader in the system with nonlinearity parameters $(\epsilon, B) = (1.0, 1.0)$ compared to the system with nonlinearity parameters $(\epsilon, B) = (4.0, 1.0)$.

Figure 3 shows the mutual information (MI) in systems of driven systems of GL with without coupling (panels A-C), with purely dissipative (panels D-F) and dissipative and reactive coupling (panels G-I). For a low amplitude of the driving force, the mutual information was mainly distributed around a small number of oscillators in the uncoupled system (panel A) or across the diagonal in the coupled systems (panels D,G), indicating that mainly neighbored oscillators share similarity. With increasing driving force, all systems showed a clear rectangular structure. For the coupled systems (panels D-I), the diagonal structure was largely unaffected, and the rectangular structure emerged around the oscillators close to the driving force frequency. In contrast to the uncoupled system, the coupled systems showed peaks of high MI for the oscillators at the edges of the cluster. In the presence of combined dissipative and reactive coupling, the distribution of MI was different compared to the other systems (Fig. 3G-I). For a small amplitude of the external driving force (panel G), mutual information was distributed not only to nearest neighbours, but also to all oscillators in a specific cluster. For an increased amplitude of the driving force (panel H), the mutual information was concentrated in a narrow region around the oscillators close to the frequency of the driving force. For the highest driving force (panel I), maxima of MI emerged at the edges of the cluster, similar to the systems with only dissipative coupling (compare to panel F). The mutual information between each oscillator and the driving force was strongly dependent on the coupling. In the uncoupled system (J-L), the MI showed a narrow distribution with one dominant peak. The dissipatively coupled system (M-O) showed broader distributions of MI and a bimodal distribution. The dissipatively- and reactively coupled system (P-R) showed the broadest distribution of MI with multiple peaks.

FIGURE 3. Mutual information of two pairs of oscillators (A-I) for systems of GL oscillators (same as in Figure 2), and mutual information of each cluster and the driving force (J-R). Panels (A-C,J-L) represent systems of uncoupled driven GL oscillators. Panels (D-F,M-O) and (G-I,P-R) represent systems of coupled driven GL oscillators (same as in Figure 2 E-F and G-I). Each panel is normalized by its maximum value. Higher intensity of color indicates higher mutual information.

DISCUSSION

The results revealed that the creation of oscillator clusters shows a rich temporal dynamic structure which is reflected in mutual information between pairs of oscillators. The creation of clusters can be understood as a mutual entrainment effect which depends on the type and strength of the oscillators. Creation of clusters was found in both a relaxation type oscillator (VP) and an oscillator with harmonic oscillation characteristics (GL). Such clusters have previously been suggested to underlie the generation of SOAEs in the ear canal [15, 19] (e.g.). The tails in the distribution of τ of each oscillator in a cluster show rich diversity in the dynamic behaviour of individual oscillators. The cluster frequencies might correspond to the spectral peak in an SOAE measurement, while the individual distributions can contribute to the spectral width observed in SOAEs [20] (e.g.). The results might also be consistent with other ideas of SOAE generation based on multiple reflections [21] when abstracting the detailed generation mechanism of multiple reflection into the description of a limit cycle oscillator. Correlation between the observed distributions for the different types of systems and SOAE data might provide insights into a suitable oscillator model of the oscillatory behaviour of the inner ear in the species of interest. Excitation of the oscillator systems with a driving force impacts the whole system in the distribution of clusters, both in terms of average periodicity and higher order statistical moments. The observation that clusters re-organize or vanish is consistent with the observation that SOAEs interact with external stimuli and that SOAE spectra change after suppression of individual SOAEs peaks [22, 23].

Mutual information was used to quantify the impact of clustering on information encoding. In terms of mutual information between neighbored oscillators, this might be interpreted in terms of tonotopy. In this light, tonotopy of a system of coupled oscillators is defined by the emergence of clusters, hence breaking the linear intrinsic gradient of the set of oscillators in isolation (Figure 3). In the presence of a driving force changes the tonotopic organization depending on the specific parameters of the system. The observation that the highest MI is present at the edges of a cluster and not close to the oscillator with similar intrinsic periodicity is another contrast to resonator models which would predict highest similarity based on their tuning curve. The emerging similarity of MI for dissipative (Figure 3 F) and dissipative- and reactive coupling (Figure 3 I) indicate a convergence of the behaviour of these systems for high driving amplitudes. This convergence could be utilized to link SOAE and fine structure effects to supra-threshold phenomena. The MI of the individual oscillators and the driving force clearly show broader distributions of the MI across the tonotopic axis, indicating stronger encoding of the driving force in the dynamic behaviour of the oscillators.

The presented systems had an intrinsic linear gradient of periodicity. Previous studies and more plausible models of amphibian and mammalian inner ears [9, 15] utilized exponential gradients. This difference in the gradient will affect the resulting distribution of clusters, but will not affect the other observed phenomena. The present study used particular systems of oscillators which might not be directly plausible for either mammalian or amphibian hearing. The observed phenomena might, however, be applicable for other systems that provide a nonlinear and active behaviour. Hence, this simplified approach might provide the required control and reduced complexity to design experimental paradigms using SOAE to obtain information about the oscillatory behaviour of the inner ear and to test and refine

more detailed model of inner ear processing.

CONCLUSIONS

Oscillators within a cluster show the same mean periodicity, but differences in their distributions of instantaneous winding number over time, leading to tails at the edges of clusters. Nearest-neighbour coupling affects encoding of information and leads to a complex re-distribution of the intrinsic tonotopic axis of coupled oscillating systems. Assuming that SOAEs can be described as systems of coupled oscillators, this approach can help to identify mechanical properties of inner ear processing

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

Dáibhid Ó'Maoiléidigh: I just must have missed it. What is the mutual information between? Usually it is between two things.

Bastian Epp: Thanks for asking. The picture with the boxes, that was neighboured oscillators. And the one on the side, that was with the stimulus. so trying to ask the question of "How much information is getting into the oscillator system?".

Dáibhid Ó'Maoiléidigh: And the one that showed the bimodal distribution - that was with the oscillator?

Bastian Epp: Yes - stimulus and oscillator.

Jacob McConley: I got to mini-questions. The first is: Your system is looking from the hair bundle all the way to the spike train. What is the model you are using for the membrane potential in the cell? And the second part is: Are you looking at any other metrics than the instantaneous spike rate to determine information?

Bastian Epp: First question: Verhulst et al. 2018 - that is the inner hair cell. And for the spike train information: Not yet. That will be the next step. Once we know what to look for. But we haven't done that yet, no.

Chris Bergevin: I have some general comments on your generic model. Just one thing that came up yesterday that might be useful to consider. the RevCorr technique and the Wiener kernel analysis. Because it sounds as if you put in a noise stimulus, you could do it. You know everything that is going on and you might be able to verify this and that. So it might be a nice and simple reality check to do.

Karolina Charaziak: I have some anecdotal data for you in terms of these edges: If you put a probe in my ear that, that is very active, then you can see some of my spontaneous emissions doing this "zip-up, zip-down".

Bastian Epp: Cool! Thank you! Living on the edge.

Kalpan Ved: What kind of coupling mechanism did you use? Injective coupling, diffusive coupling?

Bastian Epp: It is nearest neighbour. And we couple it either with a damping or a damping and stiffness, in mechanical terms.

Kalpan Ved: And is it directly coupled to the next?

Bastian Epp: It is always nearest neighbour. We looked at gradients, and the big picture doesn't change. You always see clusters and you see these tails.

Ernst Dalhoff: Am I right that you expect that the entrainment only happens close to threshold?

Bastian Epp: If you look at Glenis' data, and if you look at Arnol'd tongues, then no. If you increase intensity, the range of entrainment for a single oscillator is getting wider. And if I get it right, these Arnol'd tongues start overlapping. I haven't found a formalism to look at coupled systems, but the answer is that it also happens at higher intensities. It is less relevant for perception and less relevant for the response of the system.

Ernst Dalhoff: But at higher level, you have less gain and you are probably far from criticality.

Bastian Epp: That is a fantastic point: If you have more complex stimuli that are more rich, also in time, you could get this effect in time frames. And this is the key point that I want to make: If that is the key for processing of information on a mechanical level, then we have something "too much" in the filterbank models.

Ernst Dalhoff: So you would say that we shouldn't do the speech tests in static noise.

Bastian Epp: I don't want to lean out of the window that far.